

Yield components and standard heterosis for yield in some F₁ rice hybrids evaluated in Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1984 wet season.

Hybrid	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains/panicle (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Growth duration (d)	Disease or insect score ^a		Yield ^b (t/ha)	Standard heterosis to Cisadane (%)
					GM	BLS		
MR365A/BR10	23.4	74.4	22.9	120	0	0	4.8 a	27.65
MR365A/IR36	22.8	74.2	23.0	112	1	1	4.6 a	22.87
MR365A/IR52	23.2	73.1	24.0	109	1	1	4.3 b	14.63
MR365A/IR54	23.8	64.2	23.6	116	1	1	3.5 d	-7.44
MR365A/IR60	22.0	61.4	19.8	130	1	1	3.5 d	-7.97
MR365A/IR46	21.7	79.5	23.0	132	1	5	3.4 de	-9.04
MR365A/IR26	23.5	77.7	23.5	134	1	1	3.2 e	-16.22
MR365A/IR50	22.6	62.4	21.0	120	1	1	3.2 e	-15.69
Cisadane ^c	23.7	81.9	28.9	142	1	1	3.8 c	-
IR36	22.9	83.9	20.7	120	3	3	3.6 cd	-

^a Scoring based on 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice*. GM = gall midge, BLS = bacterial leaf streak. ^b Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT

^c Best check variety.

Indonesian conditions, MR365A could be used in developing F₁ rice hybrids using IR36, JR52, and BR10 as restorer lines. However, the CMS line is not stable for pollen sterility. □

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Identification of restorers and maintainers for four CMS lines of rice

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We crossed 17 cultivars of early, medium, and late duration (as male parents) with 4 cytoplasmic genetic male sterile lines (IR46830A, IR46831A, Zhen Shan 97A, and V20A) to identify their fertility restorers and maintainers.

The F₁ seeds were germinated in petri dishes, transferred to pots, and transplanted in the field 30 d after germination.

Varieties were classified on the basis of spikelet fertility in their F₁ hybrids: restorers = >80% spikelet fertility, partial restorers = 10-79%, and

Fertility restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers for 4 CMS lines. Pantnagar, India.

CMS line	Fertility restorer	Partial restorer	Maintainer
IR46830A	Narendra 1 Saket Basmati 370	IET7613 Narendra 2 Mahsuri Govind IR58 Manhar UPR82-42 Pant Dhan 6 Manhar Pant Dhan 6 UPR79-123 Govind Saket 4 Pant Dhan 4	Ratna N22 Rasi
IR46831A	-	Manhar Pant Dhan 6 UPR79-123 Govind Saket 4 Pant Dhan 4	Pant Dhan 4
Zhen Shan 97A V20A	- -	Saket 4 Pant Dhan 4	- -

maintainers = <10%.

Narendra 1, Saket 4, and Basmati 370 were effective restorers for IR46830A. Ratna, N22, and Rasi were identified as maintainers for this CMS line (see table). Pant Dhan 4 was a maintainer

for the CMS line IR46831A.

No fertility restorer was identified for Zhen Shan 97A, V20A, and IR46831A. There was segregation for fertility in the F₁ when V20A was crossed with Pant Dhan 4. □

Media conditioning to convert nonembryogenic rice calli to embryogenic calli

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We investigated the effect of media conditioning on converting rice

nonembryogenic (NE) callus to embryogenic (E) callus.

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L. cv. S201) seeds were dehulled mechanically, surface sterilized in 5% sodium hypochloride solution for 30 min, and rinsed 3 times with sterile distilled water. Seeds were sown in basal salts and vitamins of Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium supplemented with 200 mg myo-inositol/liter, 100 mg thiamine HCl/liter, 3% (wt/vol) sucrose, and

0.7% Difco Bacto agar (pH 5.7).

Cultures were incubated under complete darkness at 22 ± 2°C.

Ten-day-old seedlings were cut in 2- to 3-mm pieces and cultured in a callus formation medium consisting of germination medium supplemented with 20 μM 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D). Five petri dishes each containing pieces of four seedlings were used per treatment. All cultures were subcultured every 4 wk.

Two weeks after the second subculture, five samples of callus from each treatment were microscopically examined to identify E and NE calli (see figure, a). The E calli were smooth and yellowish and were composed of small compact cells with dense cytoplasm. The NE calli were pale and loosely packed and were composed of larger, crescent-shaped cells.

To condition the medium (5 ml of MS medium supplemented with 20 μ M 2, 4-D), 5 g E callus were subcultured to 10 15-mm petri dishes (conditioned medium). Ten petri dishes with medium but without E callus were the control (unconditioned medium). All dishes were sealed and kept in darkness for 10 d.

E calli were removed from the conditioned medium and 5 2-3 mm NE

Rice somatic embryogenesis: a) E callus vs NE callus formed in cultures; b) a normal somatic embryo with distinct coleoptile (CP), coleorhiza (CR), and scutellum (SC), $\times 80$; c) plants grown from somatic embryos, $\times 0.17$.

callus pieces were transferred onto all 20 petri dishes. NE calli that produced E calli were counted after 2 wk.

No NE calli cultured in unconditioned medium produced E calli; 16% of the NE calli grown in conditioned medium produced some organized cells. Those cells were subcultured onto medium containing 2.5 μ M 2, 4-D and incubated

under dim light (30 μ E/m² per s). The nodules that were produced developed into normal-appearing embryos 2 wk after they were subcultured onto growth regulator-free differentiation media. All somatic embryos looked normal (see figure, b), germinated in 5-7 d, and produced plants (see figure, c). □

Yield potential

A path-coefficient analysis of rice panicle characters

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The relationship between high density (HD) grains (those with specific gravity of 1.20 or higher) and other panicle characters could be an effective selection criterion,

We studied 50 panicles from 9 parents, 50 panicles from 6 F₁s, and 250

panicles from F₂s. HD grain index (HDI) was calculated by dividing the number of HD grains by the total number of spikelets per panicle on primary and secondary branches. Path-coefficient analysis was used to assess the direct and indirect influence of different panicle characters on HDI on primary branches (HDIPB).

The number of primary branches and number of spikelets on primary branches had a strong positive association with HDIPB in all generations (see table). Those characters are probably controlled by an additive gene action. The number of secondary

Direct (underlined) and indirect effects of associated traits on high density grain index on primary branches (HDIFB).^a IRRI, 1988.

Trait	Generation	Tiller	PB	SB	SPB	SSB	StPB	StSB	HDISB	r
Tiller	P	<u>-0.19</u>	-0.02	-	-0.01	-	0.01	-0.02	0.64	0.40*
	F ₁	<u>0.26</u>	0.02	-	0.03	0.01	-	-	0.34	0.65**
	F ₂	<u>0.04</u>	0.01	-0.01	-0.01	0.01	0.01	-0.04	0.23	0.39**
Primary branch (PB)	P	-0.03	<u>-0.14</u>	0.04	0.28	-	-0.01	-0.11	0.38	0.44**
	F ₁	0.07	<u>0.08</u>	-	0.07	-	0.01	-	0.26	0.49**
	F ₂	-	<u>0.14</u>	-0.02	-0.10	0.03	0.06	-0.02	0.20	0.31**
Secondary branch (SB)	P	-	<u>-0.09</u>	<u>0.06</u>	0.24	0.01	0.02	-0.22	0.33	0.34*
	F ₁	0.01	-	-	0.01	0.13	-0.07	-	-0.15	-0.07
	F ₂	0.01	0.08	<u>-0.04</u>	-0.05	0.06	0.05	-0.01	0.06	0.17*
Spikelet on PB (SPB)	P	-	-0.11	0.04	<u>0.34</u>	-	-0.03	-0.11	0.39	0.54**
	F ₁	0.07	0.06	-	<u>0.11</u>	-	0.02	-	0.31	0.56**
	F ₂	-	0.13	-0.02	<u>-0.15</u>	0.03	0.09	-0.02	0.21	0.31**
Spikelet on SB (SSB)	P	0.01	-0.09	0.05	0.24	<u>0.01</u>	0.02	-0.22	0.40	0.43*
	F ₁	0.01	-	-	-	<u>-0.18</u>	-0.08	-	-0.19	-0.17
	F ₂	0.01	0.07	-0.04	-0.05	<u>0.07</u>	0.05	-0.01	0.03	0.13
Sterility on PB (StPB)	P	-0.02	0.01	0.01	-0.09	-	<u>0.11</u>	-0.33	-0.08	-0.39*
	F ₁	-	-	-	-0.01	0.06	<u>-0.23</u>	0.01	-0.32	-0.49**
	F ₂	-0.01	-0.02	0.01	0.03	-0.01	<u>-0.36</u>	0.16	-0.48	-0.70**
Sterility on SB (StSB)	P	-0.01	-0.03	0.03	0.08	-	0.09	<u>-0.44</u>	0.15	-0.13
	F ₁	-0.01	-0.01	-	-0.01	0.05	-0.20	<u>0.01</u>	-0.37	-0.56**
	F ₂	-0.01	-0.01	-	0.01	-	-0.28	<u>0.22</u>	-0.56	-0.63**
HDI on SB (HDISB)	P	-0.13	-0.06	0.02	0.14	-	-0.01	-0.07	<u>0.91</u>	0.81**
	F ₁	0.14	0.03	-	0.05	-0.06	0.12	-	<u>0.61</u>	0.90**
	F ₂	0.01	0.03	-	-0.03	-	0.22	-0.15	<u>0.81</u>	0.89**

^a - indicates value almost equal to zero. Residual effects: parent (P), 0.41; F₁, 0.31; F₂, 0.39.